

Supplementary figures and tables for

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TABLE S1: CLIMATE CABINET CONDITIONS		
DAYLENGTH (HOURS)	Mean temp. (°C)	CI
17	18.37	0.003214
17.4	18.39	0.00296
17.8	18.80	0.002889
18.2	18.66	0.007015
18.6	18.38	0.004027

TABLE S2: NUMBER OF INDIVIDUALS WITHIN EACH CROSS.				
CROSS	Families	Individuals	Males	Females
GG	13	58	34	24
SS	15	71	27	44
SG	21	211	115 (112)	96
GS	21	179	98	81
SKXSU		86	48	38
SUXSK		85 (83)	37 (36)	48 (47)

The crosses GG, SS, SG and GS are from the present study while SKxSU and SUXSK are from the study by Pruischer et al. (2018). Numbers in parentheses are indicating when there were fewer individuals tested for the pupal decision.

TABLE S3: FINAL MODELS IN THE STATISTICAL ANALYSES		
ANALYSIS	larval decision	pupal decision
PURE POPULATION CROSSES AND HYBRID CROSSES GG, SS, (SG+GS)	Diapause ~ Treatment + Cross + Sex + (1 Family)	Diapause ~ Treatment + Cross + Sex + (1 Family)
RECIPROCAL HYBRID CROSSES SG, GS	Diapause ~ Treatment + Cross + Sex + Cross:Sex + (1 Family)	Diapause ~ Treatment + Cross + Sex + Cross:Sex + (1 Family)
COMPARISONS BETWEEN EXPERIMENTS SG, GS, SN, NS	Diapause ~ Father_origin + Sex + Exp + Father_origin:Sex:Exp	Diapause ~ Father_origin + Sex + Exp + Father_origin:Exp + Father_origin:Sex:Exp

TABLE S4: SENSITIVITY TEST, LARVAL DECISION			
ANALYSIS	Dependent variables	X ² (df) (36/44days)	P (36/44days)
PURE POPULATION CROSSES AND HYBRID CROSSES GG, SS, (SG+GS)	Treatment	91.22(1)/91.73(1)	<0.001/<0.001
	Cross	34.91(2)/39.39(2)	<0.001/<0.001
	Sex	17.30(1)/15.76(1)	<0.001/<0.001
RECIPROCAL HYBRID CROSSES SG, GS	Treatment	77.93(1)/77.54(1)	<0.001/<0.001
	Cross	1.82(1)/1.90(1)	0.1771/0.1685
	Sex	12.02(1)/10.83(1)	<0.001/<0.001
	Cross:Sex	0.46(1)/0.17(1)	0.4959/0.6826
COMPARISONS BETWEEN EXPERIMENTS SG, GS, SN, NS	Father_origin	98.34(1)/9.26(1)	0.0039/0.0023
	Sex	18.27(1)/16.33(1)	<0.001/<0.001
	Exp	24.40(1)/18.40(1)	<0.001/<0.001
	Father_origin:Sex:Exp	11.07(4)/11.51(4)	0.0258/0.0214

TABLE S5: CONTINGENCY TABLE		
LARVAL DECISION		
PUPAL DECISION	0	1
	0	179
1	0	201

Figure S1. Frequency histogram showing number of individuals per larval development time in days. Only individuals from the present study are included. The red arrow indicates where the cut off was for deciding whether an individual had chosen to diapause (>40 days) or not (= $<$ 40 days). Bin range =1.